

Chemical consequences of the ground-state conformations of cyclooctyl rings. Examples of reactivity differences in α -hydroxy and α,α' -dihydroxy eight-membered cyclic ketones[†]

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A program directed toward the elucidation of various conformational factors that control reactivity differences in cyclooctyl and cyclooctenyl systems is described. This overview reports on the divergent reactivity observed in the alkylation of saturated and unsaturated α -ketols. When the eight-membered ring is saturated, only C-alkylation operates. In contrast, the presence of a C5-C6 double bond allows only for O-alkylation. The central issues associated with the stereochemical course of the α,α' -dihydroxylation of cyclooctanone are also presented, as are possible complications brought on by operation of the α -ketol rearrangement. Finally, the structural requirements for the generation of a novel epoxycarbonate derivative are outlined.

Introduction

Recognition by Derek Barton of the interrelationship between the preferred chair-like conformation of cyclohexanes and the reactivity of axially- or equatorially-disposed substituents bonded thereto was a major early development in our appreciation of the behavior of structurally biased systems¹. The extent to which this insightful analysis was adopted by the organic chemical community can be gauged by the rather extensive coverage contained in a review of the subject only fifteen years later². Although three-dimensional relationships can sometimes be intricate, great strides have been made in our understanding of these problems. This is particularly true in the area of absolute stereochemical control. Whereas the ploys required to set up remote diastereomeric relationships in cyclohexane networks are now well appreciated³, considerably less attention has been accorded to medium-ring compounds⁴.

In this overview, attention is focused on functionalized eight-membered ring systems. The parent hydrocarbon of this medium-ring class features a boat-chair energy minimum (**1**)⁵, an arrangement also favored by cyclooctanone

(**2**)⁶. The distribution of torsional angles and transannular interactions in **2** conspire to cause the reduction of its carbonyl group to be more difficult than normal⁶. Similarly, the tendency of **2** to enter into cyanohydrin formation is notably inhibited ($K_{eq} = 1.2$) relative to cyclohexanone ($K_{eq} = 1000$)⁷. The structural environments in the two ketones are clearly very different, a feature that can be expected to persist as one progresses around the medium-sized ring. Indeed, it is widely recognized that the conformations of cyclooctane rings are such that many of the relationships between diastereomers are diminished or reversed with respect to those found in cyclohexane rings². However, these features do not eliminate the potential for the control of diastereomeric relationships when simple cyclooctyl compounds are involved. As Still and Galynker have pointed out⁸, several properties inherent to these systems lend themselves in a profound way to attaining high-level diastereoselection in a number of reactions. These features include the wholesale adoption of conformations having minimal nonbonded transannular repulsions and high-energy torsional arrangements. Additionally, when adjacent trigonal centers are present in eight-membered rings, these tend to orient themselves perpendicular to the plane of the ring. A major consequence, as reflected in *cis*-cyclooctene, is that the two faces of the π bond are sterically shielded to very different levels. Peripheral attack would be expected

[†]This paper is submitted in memory of Professor S. M. Mukherji for his outstanding contributions to organic chemistry and his dedication to the teaching of chemistry students.

to be kinetically dominant to an overwhelming degree. Under the proper circumstances, high asymmetric induction can therefore be anticipated.

The kinetically controlled methylation of enolate anion **4** and the conjugate addition of lithium dimethylcuprate to **6** constitute illustrative examples⁸. Here the combination of sterically different π -surfaces and the conformational bias provided by a single methyl substituent work in unison to generate the diastereomerically distinctive dimethyl products **5** and **7**. The combination of the conformational constraints at work are seen in **A** and **B**. Molecular modeling of alternative conformations having pseudoaxial methyl groups are destabilized by more than 4 kcal/mol because of severe nonbonded interactions in both the starting compounds and the products.

The catalytic hydrogenation of enone **8** over $\text{Rh}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ is reported to give rise to a 10 : 1 mixture rich in the trans isomer **7**⁸. This finding can be understood in terms of the two ground state conformers **C** and **D**, the adoption of which in a Boltzman distribution of 93 : 7 corresponds closely to the experimental hydrogenation data.

1,5-Cyclooctanedione (**9**) has been shown by X-ray crys-

tallography to exist in a boat-chair conformation in the solid state with the carbonyl groups residing at the flagpole positions as in **E**⁹. This spatial arrangement lends itself to highly diastereoselective formation of the E,E -1,4-bis(enolate) related to **10** upon two-fold deprotonation¹⁰. Adoption of this directionality conforms to the most well suited overlap

of the flanking C-H bonds in **E**, and avoidance by the system to introduce an alternative trans double bond into the eight-membered ring at a cost of approximately 11 kcal/mol¹¹. Simmons-Smith cyclopropanation of **10** led to **11**. Proof that peripheral addition to both double bonds in **F** had occurred almost exclusively was confirmed by X-ray analysis. The ring opening of **11** to give **12** is expectedly complicated by competing epimerization¹⁰.

Divergent regioselectivity in the alkylation of eight-membered α -ketols

In the introduction, the regio- and stereoselectivities of several reactions of simple cyclooctyl systems were shown to be explainable in terms of ground-state conformational preferences. Are these examples promising indicators of the fact that further stereocontrolled reactions involving related compounds await discovery? Our response is resoundingly affirmative. Let us contrast the conformational differ-

ences that accompany the crossover from saturated α -ketol **13** to its unsaturated counterpart **14**. As gauged by MM3

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calculations, the lowest energy conformation of **13** is the hydrogen-bonded arrangement **G** (Fig. 1)¹². When this structure is examined from the perspective down the carbonyl-carbinol bond, the O=C–C–H dihedral angle is seen to be

G

steric energy = 21.1 kcal/mol

O=C–C–H dihedral angle = 106.7°

H

steric energy = 22.5 kcal/mol

O=C–C–H dihedral angle = 164.7°

I

steric energy = 23.2 kcal/mol

O=C–C–H dihedral angle = 12.3°

106.7°. This value is very close to that deemed to be ideal for maximum stereoelectronic overlap¹³. Base-promoted abstraction of this proton can on this basis be expected to occur readily. In addition, a low-energy *Z*-enolate would thereby be generated. When the hydrogen-bonding constraint is released, **H** and **I** emerge as somewhat more energetic, but nevertheless potentially attractive alternatives. However, the α -deprotonation of **H** is disadvantaged because this pathway would result in the generation of a highly strained *E*-enolate. In the case of **I**, there exists a severe misalignment with the neighboring C–H bond, such that this stereoelectronic arrangement would deter abstraction of the associated proton. Accordingly, these considerations suggest that the deprotonation of **13** with a suitable base should foster the adoption of a conformation related to **G** where coordination of both oxygens to the metal ion could operate. While enolate anion generation may well be preceded by ionization of the geminal hydroxyl, subsequent proton transfer from the adjoining C–H should occur smoothly and without a significant kinetic barrier within **G**. Effective C-alkylation should result following subsequent treatment with a suitable electrophile.

At the experimental level, treatment of **13** with 1.3 equivalents of sodium hydride in DMF at –15 to –30° followed by an allylic or benzylic halide results in exclusive conversion to products of C-alkylation. The formation of **15** and **16** is illustrative of the impressive regioselectivity of this transformation¹², especially when contrasted with the behavior of **14**.

The consequences of introducing an unsaturated linkage into the eight-membered ring as in **14** on the prevailing conformational topology are quite substantial. Under these circumstances, the lowest energy arrangement is the hydrogen-bonded structure **J** (Fig. 2). The O=C–C–H dihedral angle in **J** is 164.0°. Like **H**, this conformation suffers from an unlikely ability to experience α -deprotonation since an energetically unattractive *E*-enolate would materialize. The disposition of the α -proton in structures **K** and **L** is likewise nonconducive to enolate formation. Indeed, when **14** was processed in a manner identical to that described above, only α -alkoxy ketones exemplified by **17** and **18** were formed¹². Quite evidently, while the conversion of tetrahedral carbon to trigonal carbon at C-2 in **13** occurs readily,

Fig. 1. The three lowest energy conformations of **13**.

Fig. 2. The lowest energy conformation of 14.

this situation does not persist in **14**, presumably because of the existence of impedance to proper stereochemical alignment of the key α -proton.

The possibility that the above observations may be the end result of a facile $O \rightarrow C$ shift in the saturated series was

ruled out experimentally¹². The preparation of **19** required recourse to acidic trichloroacetimidate technology¹⁴. This

substance was recovered unchanged following exposure to several bases in THF or DMF as solvent. These studies hold importance because base-promoted 1,2-shifts of the type **19** \rightarrow **20** in α -benzyloxy ketones are known to operate under comparable conditions¹⁵. In cyclooctyl systems such as **19** and **22**, further isomerization can be made to occur, but requires that charge-separated ions be generated. Thus,

by enhancement of the reactivity of potassium hexamethyldisilazide via the co-addition of an equivalent of 18-crown-6, **19** is converted within 10 min into the symmetrical ring-contracted isomer **21**¹⁶. Since the same α -ketol can be produced by the analogous treatment of **20**, it is likely that **19** is transformed by $O \rightarrow C$ migration into **20** in advance of a second-stage rearrangement¹⁷.

When the reactivity of the cyclooctenyl counterpart **22** was examined, the parallel conversion to **23** was observed.

However, this reaction required an excess of 8 h to proceed to completion. The same rate profile was exhibited by **25**, which was in turn generated by the addition of benzylmagnesium bromide to the cyclooctenedione **24**¹⁶. Since the isomerization of α -ketols is an equilibrium-based chemical change, the above observations implicate greater thermodynamic stability for the seven-membered isomer of each pair as **21** $>$ **20** and **23** $>$ **25**. These energetic relation-

ships conform to the insight provided by MM3 calculations.

Synthetic approaches to the *cis* and *trans* isomers of α,α' -dihydroxy cyclooctanone

Medium-ring cycloalkanones bearing a pair of hydroxyl substituents on the flanks of the carbonyl group have not previously been described. Our efforts to secure pure samples of the *trans* and *cis* isomers **27** and **44**, respectively, in stereocontrolled fashion began with **14**. This α -ketol is readily available in good yield from the acid-catalyzed ring opening of 1,5-cyclooctadiene monoxide in the presence of dimethyl sulfoxide followed by treatment with diisopropylethylamine¹⁸. Starting from this vantage point, the second hydroxyl was introduced by exposure of the potassium enolate to oxygen with subsequent infusion of triethylphosphite into the reaction mixture¹⁹. Although the yield of **26** was relatively low (26% at 74% conversion), a single isomer was produced. The relative stereochemical disposition of the two OH groups in **26** was not initially obvious upon inspection of the NMR data. Recourse was

therefore made to acquire the requisite stereochemical proof by chemical means. To this end, **26** was hydrogenated, and the resulting **27** was reduced with lithium aluminum hydride. Should the original OH groups be *cis*-oriented, two symmetrical products would likely be generated and both would exhibit five ¹³C NMR signals and two sets of ¹H NMR signals in the δ 4.5–3.5 region. In contrast, hydride reduction of the *trans* isomer would generate a single unsymmetrical triol requiring eight carbon signals. The lower symmetry criteria were uniquely accommodated by **28**, which must therefore possess the indicated stereochemistry. The generation of **26** in this manner is consistent with the MM3-derived minimum energy conformation of the enol of **14** (Fig. 3), with electrophilic approach materializing from its less hindered face.

In view of the inefficiency associated with the direct oxygenation of **14**, possible alternative routes for improving the acquisition of *trans* isomer **27** were next accorded attention. Silylation of **13** followed by generation of the silyl enol ether and epoxidation gave rise to **29**, an immediate

Figure 3. Global minimum energy conformation of the enol of **14**. The arrow is pointed to the less hindered π -surface.

precursor of the targeted keto diol. The 2-*O*-benzyl protected derivative **30** can be regarded as an equivalently useful progenitor of **27**¹⁹.

At this point, generation of *cis*-2,8-dihydroxycyclooctanone (**44**) was pursued along two related avenues. The first to be examined involved the oxidation of **31** with the Dess-Martin periodinane to give α -diketone **32**, treat-

ment of which with zinc dust and saturated ammonium chloride solution in THF²⁰ provided **33** uniquely. Although the regioselectivity of this reduction holds interest in its own right, the apparent inertness of the “external” carbonyl toward this reagent combination was not conducive to our goals. As before, the stereochemical features of **33** as well as **34** were convincingly established by hydride reduction to give **35**. The comparable behavior of the *O*-silylated congener **36** with a broader range of reducing agents suggests that the reactivity pattern is not entirely linked to the substituent on oxygen.

With these results in hand, it seemed advisable to pursue an entirely different tact to generate **44**. The Nysted reagent²¹ proved to be particularly well suited to the controlled olefination of **29**. However, the introduction of an external double bond in this manner was met with the co-formation of **40**, presumably as a direct consequence of the operation of a prior α -ketol rearrangement¹⁷. The three-step conversion of **40** into **38** confirmed the stereochemical assignments deduced throughout this series. Furthermore, the sequential oxidation/reduction of **39** to provide **43** in excellent overall yield allowed for access to the monoprotected *cis* diol. Ozo-

olysis of **43** gave a two-component mixture rich in **38**, indicating again the tendency for isomerization to the α -ketol characterized by the presence of an "external" carbonyl group.

This state of affairs is also operational when **37** is desilylated in the presence of fluoride ion. Although the formation of **37** predominated, this product distribution was not anticipated. The calculated (MM3) steric energies of the four isomers depicted in Fig. 4 are seen to favor the 2,8-dihydroxy arrangement in both series irrespective of the inherent stereochemical features. Intramolecular hydrogen

bonding is available to both structural classes and it is not entirely clear why the 2,3-dihydroxy ketones are 7–8 kcal/mol more sterically strained. We have established, however, that **34** and **44** are not interconverted under the reaction conditions. When **37** is reduced prior to desilylation, wholesale conversion to the cis² triol materializes as expected.

Structural requirements for epoxy carbonate formation

Conformationally unconstrained α,α' -dihydroxy ketones such as **46** react with phosgene in the presence of DMAP to form 1,3-dioxane-2,5-diones efficiently²². Crowded environments as found in **48** do not impact negatively on this reaction pathway. However, as seen in Fig. 4, the three-dimensional arrangements in **27** and **44** are more constrained

and less flexible. This feature, in tandem with the significant differences in the spatial and angular relationships of the hydroxyl substituents to the ketone carbonyl, are responsible for the adoption of quite different reaction pathways in these examples. Thus, the trans isomer reacts so as to produce the epoxy carbonate **50** where a previously unknown functional group has become incorporated. The structural features in **50** are compatible with the spectroscopic features, most particularly the infrared carbonyl absorption (1819 cm⁻¹) and the chemical shifts of the carbonate are acetal carbons (δ 151.5 and 111.6, respectively). This chemical property is not shared by cis isomer **44**.

steric energy = 23.9 kcal

steric energy = 21.8 kcal

steric energy = 30.1 kcal

steric energy = 30.0 kcal

Fig. 4. Global minimum energy conformations of the 2,8- and 2,3-dihydroxy cyclooctanones.

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